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Academic Journey of Students in Learning Mathematics under National Learning Camp

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Abstract

This phenomenology study aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of students in learning mathematics under national learning camp. Using purposive sampling, the participating 14 mathematics students in the learning camp from public school were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: difficulty in understanding math problems and concepts; having the feeling of satisfaction and fun in learning mathematics; collaborative learning enhances mathematical understanding; and lack of self-confidence causing learning deficiency. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: embodying the practical importance of mathematics; teacher support and motivation; emulating positive mindset and perseverance; and practicing self-preparation strategies, they arrived at the following insights: reflections on the importance of active learning and persistence; perseverance and growth mindset in mathematics; integration of technology for enhanced engagement and learning; and overcoming math challenges through effort and engagement. The results of this study were anticipated to be meaningful and important to the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *students in learning mathematics under learning camp, mathematics, phenomenology approach, qualitative, Philippines*

Introduction

The prevailing challenge within learning camps pertains to students' perceptions of mathematics as a difficult subject to master, reflecting a widespread concern in mathematics education. This overarching issue goes beyond the surface difficulties associated with the subject, encompassing various impediments that hinder students' progress in comprehending mathematical concepts. Mathematics, valued for its interdisciplinary nature, holds a prominent position in educational settings worldwide, amplifying the significance of addressing challenges encountered within these learning environments. Moreover, the struggles in mastering mathematics extend to encompass students' deficiencies in regulatory skills, including the management of learning environments, goal setting, and the utilization of effective study strategies (Rameli, et al., 2019).

Moreover, in the United States, over a third of 15-year-olds are classified as low performers, unable to complete fundamental tasks such as comparing distances or converting currencies. For students participating in learning camps, the situation can be even more challenging, as these camps are often designed to address significant learning gaps. Many students come into these programs with a history of struggles in mathematics, compounded by low confidence and a lack of engagement during the regular school year. The percentage of students performing at the lowest level has risen from 26% in 2012 to 36% in 2022, underscoring the need for more effective interventions in these settings. Learning camps must be structured not only to close academic gaps but also to cultivate perseverance and a growth mindset, so students can build both competence and confidence in their mathematical abilities. (Verschaffel., 2020).

Furthermore, in the Philippines, a significant challenge within the educational landscape revolves around the strikingly low performance levels observed among students during the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). This concerning trend, notably evident in mathematics, reveals a disheartening reality where fewer than 20% of students attained the minimum proficiency level (Level 2), while over 50% struggled below Level 1, showcasing very low proficiency. Amidst these challenges, learning mathematics within the camp poses hurdles, hindering students' effective grasp of fundamental mathematical concepts. This educational scenario places Filipino students at a substantial disadvantage compared to their global counterparts, with a majority lacking essential mathematical skills. Moreover, the disparities in mathematical achievement between students in public and private schools underscore the complexity of this issue, necessitating targeted interventions aimed at bridging these gaps and uplifting the overall mathematical proficiency of Filipino students. (Bernardo, 2022).

The statement emphasizes the pivotal role of understanding the program's effectiveness within the broader scope of fostering critical thinking skills and cultivating a holistic educational experience. This study is instrumental in shaping educational policies and practices aimed at bolstering students' overall mathematical proficiency, essential for their academic success and broader skill development. The urgency in examining students' mathematics learning within national learning camps arises from the imperative need to comprehensively evaluate the program's impact and offer informed insights for educational decision-making. By scrutinizing the national learning camp's influence, the study aims to discern strengths, weaknesses, and areas necessitating improvement in the mathematics teaching approach. This assessment is critical not only for refining existing strategies but also for tailoring educational initiatives to better address the diverse challenges students encounter while learning mathematics in these learning camps.

Despite various perspectives on learning difficulties in mathematics within learning camps, a significant gap remains in comprehensive

research on this specific issue. Studies such as those by Lynch and Mancenido (2023) in "The Impact of Summer Programs on Student Mathematics Achievement" and Maguate and Ohoylan (2023) in "Efficacy of National Learning Camp to Literacy and Numeracy of Grade 7 Learners" offer valuable insights but address different dimensions. Lynch and Mancenido (2023) found that summer programs can enhance students' mathematics achievement, though the extent of improvement is closely linked to the quality of instruction and student engagement. Their findings suggest that interactive and targeted teaching methods are more effective, although students with significant foundational gaps may continue to face challenges. In contrast, Maguate and Ohoylan (2023) reported that a national learning camp positively impacted literacy and numeracy among Grade 7 learners, highlighting the effectiveness of structured learning environments. This study aims to explore students' experiences within the framework of the national learning camp implementation. Its timeliness and relevance align with the research agenda and priority outlined in the Department of Education's DepEd Order No. 14, s.2023, known as the Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of the National Learning Camp. In contrast to previous research, this study will adopt a qualitative, phenomenological approach, emphasizing the need for dedicated research into students' learning experiences in mathematics within the context of a national learning camp.

Upon completion of this research, the researcher plans to submit the research paper to the Department of Education (DepEd). The goal is to provide valuable insights for enhancing mathematical learning camps and to offer foundational groundwork that enables the DepEd to devise strategies and policies for more effective mathematics learning environments, thereby aiding students in improving their mathematical abilities. Additionally, the researcher intends to publish this study with the vision of it serving as a fundamental resource for other academics interested in extending this inquiry to broader national or international levels. The researcher also plans to present the findings at various conferences, aiming to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges students face in mathematical learning camps. This dissemination will not only provide a significant point of reference but also act as a catalyst for further investigations, enhancing comprehension of students' difficulties in diverse educational settings beyond the local scope of Kapalong.

Research Questions

This study aims to find out and understand the experiences of school principal, mathematics teacher, parents, and student in the implementation of the national learning camp. Therefore, important questions that was tackled are as follows:

1. What are the experiences of students in learning mathematics under national learning camp?
2. How do these students cope with the challenges in learning mathematics under national learning camp?
3. What insights can be obtained from these students who are learning mathematics under national learning camp that can be shared to other students and to the academe in general?

Methodology

Research Design

The research employed a qualitative research design to explore the real-life experiences of students in learning mathematics. Qualitative research encompasses a wide variety of methods and approaches, each with its unique focus, assumptions about knowledge, and the researcher's role. Additionally, employing multiple qualitative data collection methods enhances our comprehension of the individuals under study, their life narratives, and experiences (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

In this study, qualitative research was utilized to uncover the underlying meanings and interpretations behind actions or outcomes typically measured by quantitative research. In contrast to quantitative research, which focuses on numerical data and statistical analysis, qualitative research explores the symbolic, interpretive, and relational aspects of social life. Consequently, the researchers in this study examined the experiences, perspectives, and coping mechanisms of students in learning mathematics.

Meanwhile, a phenomenological approach was also employed to gain insights and identify the underlying phenomenon by examining the viewpoints of individuals involved in the given situation. This research chooses the phenomenological approach to investigate the behavior of students in learning mathematics. Phenomenology is the study of the structures of consciousness as they are experienced from a first-person perspective. At its core, an experience has a purpose, meaning that it is oriented toward something, serving as an experience of or about that thing. An experience's direction towards an object is facilitated by its content or significance, which represents the object along with the necessary conditions that make this representation possible (Smith, 2017).

In this study, phenomenological approach is a well-suited choice due to its strong alignment with the study's objectives. The aim of the study was to capture the experiences of students in learning mathematics, making a phenomenological inquiry particularly relevant within this research context. At its core, phenomenology can be characterized as an exploration of the structures and consciousness of experiences. Additionally, phenomenology involves the examination of conscious experiences from a subjective or first-person perspective.

Participants

In this phenomenological study, there were fourteen (14) participants who were all enrolled in a public school under the Division of Davao del Norte. They were fourteen (14) high school students from Kapalong National High School. All of them underwent face-to-face interviews.

This approach aligns with Creswell's (2013) recommendation that a suitable number of participants in qualitative research typically falls between 3 and 15, allowing for data saturation during data collection.

The participant selection follows a purposive sampling method, ensuring that only those capable of providing relevant data were included in the study. Purposive sampling relies on specific inclusion criteria, a common practice in qualitative research to identify and select cases rich in information regarding the phenomenon under investigation. Although various purposive sampling strategies exist, criterion sampling is frequently employed in implementation research. Nevertheless, a combination of sampling strategies may better align with implementation research objectives and contemporary advances in quantitative methods (Palinkas et al., 2017).

The eligibility criteria for participants in this study were as follows: (1) enrollment at Kapalong National High School; (2) participation in a national learning camp; and (3) equal treatment of all participants, regardless of gender preferences or identities.

Procedure

To commence, the researcher initiated a rigorous manuscript review conducted by the research technical panel. Subsequently, following unanimous consent from all panel members, the researcher composed a formal permission letter addressed to the relevant institution to obtain authorization for the study. This letter was dispatched to the college president of KCAST. Upon the endorsement of the request letter, duplicates of these correspondences were provided to the College Registrar to ensure ongoing updates regarding the study's progress. To apprise the selected participants, the researcher notified them via various means, including email or any other mutually agreeable mode of communication, extending invitations for interviews based on their willingness and scheduling convenience.

To collect data for this study, the researcher conducted comprehensive interviews with participants, allowing them the flexibility to communicate in Filipino, Bisaya, English, or a blend of these three languages. Before commencing the interviews, the researcher obtained the participants' permission to record their responses using recording devices like smartphones or tape recorders. This precaution was taken to ensure the accurate preservation of the conversation and to prevent any significant information from being overlooked.

The researcher aims to gather valuable and precise information by crafting focused questions and anticipating various possible responses during the interviews. To maintain focus and prevent deviations, questionnaires were prepared to assist the participants during the interviews. These interview questions underwent rigorous scrutiny by a panel of experts to ensure their alignment with the study's overarching themes.

Furthermore, the researcher diligently recorded all participants' choices and feedback to provide pertinent data for the study. Ensuring the confidentiality of the participants was a top priority for the researcher, accomplished by storing the data in securely protected files with passwords. This commitment to confidentiality represented a critical step in the research, guaranteeing the protection of participants' personal information.

Data Analysis

In this research, the collected data is carefully examined and analyzed in accordance with the research objectives and requirements. This entails a comprehensive analysis of the content within the participants' responses to derive the study's findings. The process of data analysis involves scrutinizing, refining, transforming, and modeling data to unearth valuable insights, formulate conclusions, and facilitate decision-making. Moreover, the goal of data analysis is to uncover common patterns and themes in human experiences, and this iterative process continues with each new interview or account until all have been compared.

Qualitative data analysis is a systematic procedure for organizing and examining various data forms, such as interview transcripts and observation notes, to gain a deeper understanding of a specific phenomenon. This undertaking can be demanding and time-consuming, as it requires the researcher to unearth the underlying meanings behind participants' actions and reactions. Despite the presence of advanced analysis tools, the researcher remains the principal instrument in extracting these meanings through in-depth engagement with both the data and the participants. While various qualitative methodologies may adopt different approaches, the fundamental phases of content analysis remain consistent, encompassing data preparation, thorough reading and reflection, coding, categorization, and theme development. Throughout this analytical process, the researcher progresses from describing the phenomenon to conceptualizing and abstracting themes, all while preserving the participants' voices who shared their stories. Maintaining the confidentiality of participants is of utmost importance during the data analysis phase (Ravindran, 2019).

To initiate the data collection process, a purposive sampling strategy was employed. Participants were selected based on direct observation, resulting in the inclusion of fourteen high school students learning mathematics under the national learning camp in the study. These participants willingly signed a consent form, expressing their agreement with the study's conditions and their willingness to share their knowledge and experiences, which were deemed highly valuable for the research.

The primary participants were individually briefed about the project prior to the interviews, which aimed to collect data for the study. The interviews began with an introduction, followed by an overview of the meeting's objectives and scope, emphasizing confidentiality and duration. Detailed information was provided to the participants regarding the recording process, including technical aspects and the rationale for recording the sessions.

Furthermore, the study employed thematic analysis due to its versatility in extracting new insights and concepts from qualitative data. A notable advantage of thematic analysis is its accessibility, making it user-friendly, particularly for novice researchers (Braun, 2006).

Once the data was obtained, a thorough review was conducted multiple times before transcribing it into a Word document. Subsequently, the transcript was closely examined multiple times to enhance comprehension of the data. The next step involved the identification and labeling of ideas in the data, known as coding. Similar ideas were then grouped into categories or themes. Finally, relationships between various ideas and themes were established.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical codes are established to ensure the ethical conduct of scientific research. In this study, paramount importance was placed on how ethical principles were observed and applied to the participants and the overall research setting, ensuring the well-being and trust of both parties. Special attention was directed towards individuals with whom the researcher had no prior relationship, and measures were taken to guarantee their safety and provide them with complete protection to sustain their interest.

Consequently, the primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard the safety and trust of all participants. The study adhered to a set of ethical guidelines, including respect for individuals, promoting their well-being, ensuring fairness, upholding confidentiality, and obtaining informed consent, as outlined by scholars like Boyatzis (1998) and Mack et al. (2005).

Respect for person entails the researcher's commitment to avoid exploiting any vulnerabilities or weaknesses of research participants, emphasizing the importance of maintaining trust, friendship, and confidence between the participants and the researcher while avoiding any form of dependency. In line with this principle, an informed consent form was thoughtfully prepared and provided to participants in advance. This form was designed to inform anyone interested, including administrators from the participants' schools, universities, and colleges, about the study's progress as a sign of respect for all those involved (Creswell, 2013).

Throughout the research process, I established a sense of courtesy and rapport with my participants. I ensured that I obtained their consent before documenting the in-depth interviews (IDI). They were given the opportunity to ask questions at any point, whether before, during, or after the interviews. Furthermore, I emphasized to them the utmost confidentiality of all upcoming IDI session, stressing that this session would remain confidential and undisclosed to the general public.

Benevolence underscores the researcher's commitment to minimizing risks to participants rather than maximizing gains for the study. To safeguard the participants, their identities were kept confidential throughout the interviews. Comprehensive measures were in place to ensure the continuous protection of participants, with all information files securely stored and supervised (Bricki & Green, 2007).

Throughout the research, I, the researcher, took precautions to safeguard the participants' identities by using pseudonyms to anonymize their statements and responses, preserving their confidentiality. Moreover, the interview guide was thoughtfully crafted to avoid sensitive or irrelevant topics that could potentially cause discomfort or anxiety among participants. I made it a priority to ensure that participants did not express any discomfort while responding to interview questions throughout the study.

Justice as part of the research process, it is essential to make a fair assessment of the risks and benefits associated with the study's findings. Recognizing and acknowledging the contributions of all participants is of utmost importance, as they play an integral role in the research's success. It is crucial to provide due credit for their involvement in the research endeavor. Additionally, during the interview phase, participants were not subjected to any financial burdens. To express gratitude for their valuable contributions to the study, practical tokens of appreciation were offered (Crabtree and Bloom, 2006).

Throughout the execution of this research, the researcher ensures that all participants are treated with fairness and equality. Benefits and potential risks associated with the research were distributed equitably among all participants, with a primary focus on ensuring their comfort and willingness to participate. Furthermore, as a gesture of recognition for their effort and participation, practical gifts and tokens of appreciation were provided to the participants.

Confidentiality is crucial in safeguarding the outcomes, conclusions, and the identities of the participants. To ensure confidentiality, a coding system was implemented to anonymize participant information, effectively concealing their identities. Following the data evaluation process, all materials, including audio recordings, encoded transcripts, notes, and related documents, were securely disposed of. Initially, some participants hesitated to participate in the interviews due to uncertainty about what to disclose, but their concerns were alleviated when the researcher assured them that their responses would be treated with utmost confidentiality, eventually making them feel at ease when responding to interview questions (Maree and Van Der Westhuizen, 2007).

During the interviews, it is worth noting that a few participants exhibited apprehension in answering questions. However, I, as the researcher, consistently reassured them that their responses would be handled with strict confidentiality. It was emphasized that participants were under no obligation to disclose information and that their participation was voluntary.

Consent is another vital approach to demonstrate genuine concern for individuals throughout the research process involves ensuring that participants are well-informed about the research study's objectives and goals in which they are taking part. Participants will be provided with written permission forms to obtain their explicit consent. Following their affirmation, they were invited to engage in in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Furthermore, participants were assured that they would be informed about the study's

findings and results, in line with ethical considerations (Creswell, 2013)

In his own practice, the researcher makes it a priority to show respect to the participants by seeking their voluntary participation in the research. Additionally, the researcher will distribute an informed consent letter to participants, outlining the data collection process and emphasizing the thorough protection of their gathered information. Importantly, participants who will choose not to participate in the study are given the option to withdraw, with a guarantee that their information would remain confidential even after the study's completion.

Results and Discussion

This section is divided into four parts. Part, one focuses on the participants' data, from which qualitative data were collected. Part two covers the data analysis procedures and the steps involved in categorizing the emergent themes from the results of the in-depth interviews. Part three focuses on the responses to the interview questions pertaining to each research problem. Lastly, part four provides a summary of the responses.

Participants

The participants of this study were the students in learning mathematics under National Learning Camp in Kapalong National High School of Davao del Norte. As shown in Table 1, a total of 14 individuals took part in this study, comprising 14 participants for the in-depth interview.

In-depth Interview. There were fourteen key participants in this study. All of these participants were students in KNHS who are under National Learning Camp located in, Davao del Norte. To uphold the principle of confidentiality, each participant was assigned a pseudonym during the in-depth interview, following the approach employed by Bernal (2014). These pseudonyms were chosen by the participants themselves based on their preferences and the unique characteristics that emerged during the interview sessions.

The selected pseudonyms provided insight into the characteristics and qualities of the participants. For instance, Fluent, acquired his nickname due to his adeptness in responding, Active was named due to his agility in responding during the interview. Dynamic was chosen for the participant who skillfully juggled busy schedules while learning. Effortful received her nickname due to her relentless efforts in learning. Caring earned her nickname because of her genuine concern for his academic progress and consistent support. Passionate was bestowed upon him in recognition of his unwavering dedication and fervor towards his pursuits. Resourceful epitomizes her adept problem-solving skills and innovative resource utilization.

Furthermore, Cool Composure was selected for the participant who consistently maintained a calm and relaxed demeanor while learning and solving math problems. Vocabulary is her nickname due to her proficiency in using words and understanding problem-solving concepts. Smart Joker is his nickname because he excels in entertaining while also being proficient in solving mathematical problems. Knowledgeable is her nickname as she exhibits brightness and possesses a wealth of knowledge in mathematics and other subjects. Fast Learner is her nickname due to his rapid acquisition and comprehension of mathematical concepts. Tenacious earned his nickname for his determination to grasp essential concepts, particularly in understanding mathematics. Lastly, Optimistic was the pseudonym for another because of her resilient attitude, and proactive approach towards challenges and opportunities.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-depth Interview (Pseudonym)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Fluent	14	M	IDI-01
Active	15	M	IDI-02
Dynamic	16	F	IDI-03
Effortful	15	F	IDI-04
Caring	14	M	IDI-05
Passionate	16	M	IDI-06
Resourceful	17	F	IDI-07
Cool Composure	15	F	IDI-08
Vocabulary	15	F	IDI-09
Smart Joker	14	M	IDI-10
Knowledgeable	16	F	IDI-11
Fast Learner	16	M	IDI-12
Tenacious	17	M	IDI-13
Optimistic	16	F	IDI-14
Total = 14			

All participants answered the same set of questions. The selection of participants was based on their involvement and experiences as students in learning mathematics under National Learning Camp, which were identified by the researcher and verified through personal declarations provided by the participants.

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face for it to be more personal and engaging, allowing for deeper insights and better

interpretation of non-verbal cues. Additionally, immediate clarification and follow-up questions can be addressed, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the participant's experiences. Most of the participants did ask for a hardcopy which was distributed to their schools as per request. The researcher respected the participant's decision when asked to adjust and reschedule the interview due to their important reasons related to their classes. The researcher did consider face-to-face as an important factor to consider in achieving and ensuring the validity and credibility of the study.

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews, the interview responses were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis commenced with the coding process, which involved organizing the materials into segments of texts to derive meaningful information. Through coding, descriptions of the participants' settings and thematic categories were generated to shape an overall depiction of the phenomenon under study. Data results were presented in the form of a table. This data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted to vividly describe the emerged themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants' responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

In the data analysis, we followed the second step by categorizing the data and presenting it in Table 2. The themes were organized according to the research questions and referred to as central themes, while the opposing significant themes were represented as co-ideas from the participants' responses. Additionally, the table included a column indicating the frequency of the responses, which served as the basis for classifying them into general, typical, and variant categories, as discussed above.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of students in learning mathematics under national learning camp?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences in learning mathematics under National Learning Camp.

Table 2. *Experiences of Students in Learning Mathematics under National Learning Camp*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Difficulty in Understanding Math Problems and Concepts	<p>"In my opinion, the challenges that I have perceived in the learning camp are that I struggle to understand certain math problems, like there are some math problems that I really need to review and learn again until I fully understand them." - IDI-01</p> <p>"For me, the challenges I perceived in learning math at the learning camp are tackling difficult math problems quickly. Especially since I am not a fast learner, it is hard for me to interact with others."- IDI-02</p> <p>"For me, since I am not proficient in math, I find it difficult to comprehend various mathematical concepts during learning, and there are many because I am not a fast learner. Math, for me, demands time and focus, and even though I put effort into it, I still struggle because I'm not a fast learner."- IDI-04</p> <p>"The challenges I have faced or noticed during my participation in the learning camp are, you know, I still find it difficult to understand what the math teacher is teaching because they teach quite fast, so I struggle to grasp what the teacher discusses." -IDI-07</p>
Having the Feeling of Satisfaction and Fun in learning Mathematics	<p>"The positive thing I learned is that I used to struggle to understand mathematics, feeling that some discussions were impossible to grasp. However, the learning camp was really beneficial because I learned a lot and also enjoyed the activities we did, especially since there were free snacks available." IDI-01</p> <p>When there is a math-related game at the learning camp, it is fun because we collaborate, and this is one reason why I enjoy studying math even though I am not very good at it. Because of this, I gradually developed my math skills at the learning camp." IDI-02</p> <p>"In the learning camp, one of the positive things I have learned about math is that it gives me time, especially, I can focus on the math subject, and I can learn more while staying here in the learning camp, and one thing I like about it is that it's fun." IDI-04</p> <p>"It was enjoyable, and I am glad I participated because I was also prepared for the challenges in math." IDI-13</p>
Collaborative Learning Enhances Mathematical Understanding	<p>"In that part where we are given activities, we collaborate to solve problems in the learning camp, and it's fun because I do not feel bored with math anymore since it can be related and easier to understand, especially when we cooperate in the activity ourselves" -IDI-01</p> <p>"The part of the learning camp that I enjoyed was when there were activities and math games, and we needed to collaborate and take turns answering. For me, it is because I find studying math easier to understand when I'm happy. That is why I really enjoyed the learning camp." IDI-02</p> <p>"Perhaps, because there were times when we all reacted simultaneously, like realizing the usefulness of what we were taught in the learning camp, which made us collaborate even more. You realize that it is because of the fun activities and math games." IDI-05</p>
Lack of Self-confidence Causing Learning Deficiency	<p>"The reason for my lack of confidence is that I find it difficult to learn because I do not cooperate. I am also too shy to ask about things I do not understand. That is why it is harder because I feel embarrassed to ask"- IDI-03</p> <p>"One thing I want to mention is that I lack confidence in myself, which is why I cannot give attention to the</p>

task given to me. There are times when I have time to study and learn about it, but we choose not to study and do things that are not very important, especially those that are difficult to do.” - IDI-04
 “I do not have friends to join in learning, which makes me feel even more embarrassed because I lack confidence in interacting. I also do not get a chance to express myself, which makes me feel sad.” -IDI-08
 “Getting a wrong answer when called upon feels embarrassing to me. Other students may look up to you when you answer questions correctly during recitations, so making even one mistake feels significant and unexpected. As a result, I hesitate to raise my hand, even when I know the answer, because my confidence has already been shaken.” – IDI- 13

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, four major themes had emerged: Difficulty in Understanding Math Problems and Concepts, Having the Feeling of Satisfaction and Fun in learning Mathematics, Collaborative Learning Enhances Mathematical Understanding, and Lack of Self-confidence Causing Learning Deficiency.

Difficulty in Understanding Math Problems and Concepts

The theme focuses the formidable challenge many students encounter in comprehending mathematical problems and concepts, forming the cornerstone of our learning camp's mission. Recognizing the pervasive nature of this obstacle, the learning camp is meticulously designed to provide targeted support and guidance to address these difficulties head-on. Through a blend of rigorous instruction, interactive exercises, and individualized attention, their aim is to cultivate a deeper understanding and mastery of mathematical principles. By fostering an environment that prioritizes critical thinking, problem-solving techniques, and practical application, they strive to empower students to overcome hurdles and embrace the complexities of mathematics with confidence and proficiency.

Based on the experience of Fluent (pseudonym) He narrated the challenges he perceived in the learning camp, expressing difficulty in understanding math problem. Additionally, Fluent (pseudonym) this suggests that he needs to review and learn again to grasp the concepts in math, he mentioned:

“Sa akoo ya kanang ang challenges na akong na perceived sa learning camp ya kay mag lisod kog sabot sa kuti na problem sa math ya like naay uban na problem sa math na need jud balikbalikon nakog tuon hantod makabalo nako.” (IDI-01)

(In my opinion, the challenges that I have perceived in the learning camp are that I struggle to understand certain math problems, like there are some math problems that I really need to review and learn again until I fully understand them.)

As with the other participant, Active (pseudonym) He narrated his challenges in tackling mathematics problems quickly, and he actively participates in recitations. Additionally, Active (pseudonym) emphasized that it is hard for him to interact with other people, he shared:

“Para sakoo kanang ang challenges nga akong na perceived sa pagtuon sa math sa learning camp kay pagkat-on sa lisod nga problem sa mathematics og paspas. Ilabi na ya nga dili ko fast learner mao nang lisod sakoo makipag halobilo sa uban ya.” (IDI-02)

(For me, the challenges I perceived in learning math at the learning camp are tackling difficult math problems quickly. Especially since I am not a fast learner, it is hard for me to interact with others.)

In addition, Effortful (pseudonym) pointed that he is not proficient in math, he finds it difficult to understand the concepts in math. Additionally, Effortful (pseudonym) emphasized that even though she puts effort in, she is still strugglin, he shared

“Para sako ya noh nga dli hawod sa math na subject, naglisud ko pagsabot gikan sa mga uban nga concept sa math learning og daghan pa kay dli ko fast learner ya. Ang math para sa akoo ya nanginahanglan siya og time og focus ug bisan pa ihatag nako na maglisud jud ko kay dili ko fast learner.” (IDI-04)

(For me, since I'm not proficient in math, I find it difficult to comprehend various mathematical concepts during learning, and there are many because I'm not a fast learner. Math, for me, demands time and focus, and even though I put effort into it, I still struggle because I'm not a fast learner.)

Lastly, Resourceful (pseudonym) persistent challenges in grasping mathematical concepts, attributing this difficulty to the teaching methodology employed. Specifically, she elucidated that the pace at which the teacher delivers the lessons poses a barrier to her comprehension, she shared:

“ahm kanang ang mga challenge na akong naagian or nakita sa akong pag apil sa learning camp kay kuan kanang maglisod gihapon kog sabot sa mga ginatudlo sa maestra sa math kay medyo paspas gihapon ang pagtudlo nila, maglisod kog sabot dayon sa gi discuss ni maam.” (IDI-07)

(The challenges I've faced or noticed during my participation in the learning camp are, you know, I still find it difficult to understand what the math teacher is teaching because they teach quite fast, so I struggle to grasp what the teacher discusses.)

Having the Feeling of Satisfaction and Fun in learning Mathematics

The theme focuses on the cultivation of a profound sense of satisfaction and enjoyment within the realm of mathematics education. It

underscores the importance of not only mastering mathematical concepts but also instilling a genuine enthusiasm for the subject. Through innovative teaching methods, interactive activities, and real-world applications, our goal is to make the learning process both rewarding and fun for students. By fostering a positive learning environment where curiosity is encouraged and achievements celebrated, we aim to inspire a lifelong love for mathematics, thereby empowering students to embrace challenges with confidence and derive fulfillment from their mathematical endeavors.

Based on the experience of Fluent (pseudonym) shared experiences indicating challenges in understanding mathematics. However, he also highlighted the positive aspects of his participation in the learning camp. Additionally, Fluent found the camp to be highly beneficial. He appreciated the opportunity to learn and engage in enjoyable activities. he mentioned:

“Ang positive nga butang na akong natunan ya kay isa man ko sa maglisod og sabot sa mathematics ya feel nako impossible na matun an ang isa ka lisod na discussion ya kaya nindot kaayo ang learning camp ya kay naa jud koy natun an og nalingaw pud sa mga activities na gina pabuhat og naay libre snacks ya.” (IDI-01)

(The positive thing I learned is that I used to struggle to understand mathematics, feeling that some discussions were impossible to grasp. However, the learning camp was really beneficial because I learned a lot and also enjoyed the activities we did, especially since there were free snacks available.)

In addition to Active's (pseudonym) experience, he highlighted the fun and collaboration in math games at the learning camp. Despite feeling less skilled, Active enjoyed these activities, which motivated his engagement with math. Through participation, he gradually improved his math skills, showing the effectiveness of collaborative learning, he shared:

“Kanang naay dula ya nga about sa math sa learning camp ya tapos lingaw siya ya kay magtinabangay mi og isa ni sa dahilan nganong ganahan ko magtuon og math ya maskin dili kayo ko hawud. Tungod ani ya nag ka hinay hinay ko og ka develop sa math sa learning camp.” (IDI-02)

(When there's a math-related game at the learning camp, it's fun because we collaborate, and this is one reason why I enjoy studying math even though I'm not very good at it. Because of this, I gradually developed my math skills at the learning camp.)

Moreover, Effortful (pseudonym) expressed that in the learning camp, one of the positive aspects she discovered about math is that it provides her with time, which allows for enhanced focus on the subject matter. Additionally, she emphasizes the significance of immersive learning experiences in fostering academic growth, she stated:

“Ahhmm sa learning camp ya, isa sa positive nga natun an sa math kay naghatag siya time sako ilabi na, maka focus ko sa math subject tapos mas matun an pa nako habang naga dugay diri sa learning camp og isa sa gusto nako ya kay kanang lingaw siya ya.” (IDI-04)

(In the learning camp, one of the positive things I've learned about math is that it gives me time, especially, I can focus on the math subject, and I can learn more while staying here in the learning camp, and one thing I like about it is that it's fun.)

Lastly, Tenacious (pseudonym) stated that participating in the learning camp was enjoyable and expressed satisfaction with their decision to join. he emphasized feeling prepared to face the challenges presented in math. he shared:

“makalingaw unya mayo lang nga niapil ko kay naka andam pod ko sa mga gilisodan sa math.” (IDI-13)

(It was enjoyable, and I'm glad I participated because I was also prepared for the challenges in math.)

Collaborative Learning Enhances Mathematical Understanding

This theme highlights the significant impact of collaborative learning on enhancing mathematical understanding among students in the learning camp. By engaging in group discussions, peer teaching, and cooperative problem-solving tasks, students deepen their comprehension and benefit from diverse perspectives. Collaborative learning fosters active participation, mutual support, and the development of essential skills like communication and critical thinking, ultimately leading to improved mathematical proficiency and a dynamic learning community within the camp.

Based on the experience of Fluent (pseudonym) underscores the positive impact of collaborative learning activities at the learning camp. Working together to solve math problems not only makes learning enjoyable but also helps him overcome boredom with math. Bold finds math easier to understand when it's related to real-life scenarios. Active participation and cooperation in activities further enhance his understanding. he mentioned:

“Sa part ya nga mag hatag na og activities kay mag tinabangay mi ya para ma solve ang problems sa learning camp ya tapos lingaw siya ya dili ko mafeel og kaboring sa math ya kay ma relate man gud siya og mas dali matun an samot na nga kami jud mismo nag cooperate sa activity.” (IDI-01)

(In that part where we are given activities, we collaborate to solve problems in the learning camp, and it's fun because I don't feel bored with math anymore since it can be related and easier to understand, especially when we cooperate in the activity ourselves.)

Additionally, Active (pseudonym) expressed his enjoyment during activities and math games at the learning camp, highlighting the

collaborative nature of these experiences. He finds studying math easier when he's happy, emphasizing the importance of a positive learning environment. Overall, Bold's positive experience underscores the value of interactive and collaborative activities in enhancing engagement and comprehension in mathematics education.

“Ang part sa learning camp nga nalingaw ko ya kanang naay mga activity og mga math games ya tapos kinahanglan mag tinabangay og paunhanay og answer ya. Kay para sako ya pag malipay ko na nagtuon og math dali ra nako siya masabtan. Mao ng naenjoy jud ko sa learning camp ya.” (IDI-02)

(The part of the learning camp that I enjoyed was when there were activities and math games, and we needed to collaborate and take turns answering. For me, it's because I find studying math easier to understand when I'm happy. That's why I really enjoyed the learning camp.)

As with the other participants, Caring (pseudonym) also expressed his perspective. He highlighted the synchronized reactions among the group during certain instances, indicating a collective realization of the practicality of the lessons taught at the learning camp. This mutual understanding fostered increased collaboration among the participants, he shared:

“siguro ya, kay tong mga times nga sabay sabay jud mig reaksyon like ma realize na kanang unsa deay kagamit ang ginatun an sa learning camp ya samot nanga mag tinabangay mi like ma realize nimo kay tungod sa mga lingaw na mga activities og mga math games.” (IDI-05)

(Perhaps, because there were times when we all reacted simultaneously, like realizing the usefulness of what we were taught in the learning camp, which made us collaborate even more. You realize that it's because of the fun activities and math games.)

Lack of Self-confidence Causing Learning Deficiency

The focus of this theme centers on the detrimental impact of lack of self-confidence on learning mathematics among students in the learning camp. When students lack confidence in their abilities, they may hesitate to engage with learning materials, avoid seeking help when needed, and may even develop a negative attitude towards learning mathematics overall. This lack of self-assurance can create barriers to effective learning, hindering students' progress and impeding their academic success in mathematics. Addressing this issue requires creating a supportive and nurturing learning environment where students feel empowered to take risks, make mistakes, and gradually build their confidence in learning mathematics.

Based on the experience of Dynamic (pseudonym) expressed challenges arising from a lack of confidence in her learning process. Her experience underscores the importance of addressing confidence issues in the learning environment to promote active participation and create a supportive atmosphere where students feel comfortable seeking help and clarifying doubts. she mentioned:

“Kuan, ya lack of confidence reason maong mas maglisod kog tuon kay wala man ko naga cooperate. too shy pud na mangutana sa mga gikalibugan nako. kaya mas mag lisod kay maulaw man mangutana.” (IDI-03)

(The reason for my lack of confidence is that I find it difficult to learn because I don't cooperate. I'm also too shy to ask about things I don't understand. That's why it's harder because I feel embarrassed to ask.)

As with the other participants, Effortful (pseudonym) also faced challenges related to confidence in her learning process. She identified a lack of self-confidence as a barrier to focusing on tasks, often leading her to skip study opportunities she perceived as unimportant or difficult. This highlights how confidence issues can affect students' motivation and engagement. Addressing these issues is crucial for creating a supportive learning environment where students feel empowered to pursue their academic goals, she shared:

“Kanang ang isa sa akong maingun ya kay wala koy kompyansa sa sarili ya mao ng di nako mahatag og attention ang gihatag sako na task kanang naa koy time nga mag study og makatuon ana na butang pero gipili namo dili magstudy og ginabuhay ang dli kaayo importante na butang ilabi na ya nga lisod ang himoonon.” (IDI-04)

(One thing I want to mention is that I lack confidence in myself, which is why I cannot give attention to the task given to me. There are times when I have time to study and learn about it, but we choose not to study and do things that are not very important, especially those that are difficult to do.)

Moreover, Cool Composure (pseudonym) expressed that she doesn't have friends to join in learning, which makes her feel even more embarrassed because she lacks confidence in interacting. She also doesn't get a chance to express herself, which makes her feel sad. she mentioned:

“kanang kuan ya wala koy mga friend nga makauban sa pag learn samot na na ulawan kayko wala koy confidence makipag halobilo tapos dili nako matagaan og chance akong sarili na kaya sad nako ya.” (IDI-08)

(I don't have friends to join in learning, which makes me feel evenmore embarrassed because I lack confidence in interacting. I also don't get a chance to express myself, which makes me feel sad.)

Tenacious (pseudonym) explained the impact of getting a wrong answer, feeling embarrassed since others may admire those who consistently answer correctly. Making a mistake feels unexpectedly heavy, causing hesitation in participating further. Despite knowing

the correct answer, he refrains from raising his hand due to a blow to his confidence. This underscores the need for a supportive classroom environment where students feel encouraged to learn from mistakes without fear of judgment, he mentioned:

“Getting a wrong answer when getting called. For me, I find it embarrassing since other students may look up to you when you get answers correct at recitations and getting one mistake feels heavy and seems very unexpected that is why I don’t to want to raise my hand eventhough I know the answer because I already lost my confidence.” (IDI-13)

(Getting a wrong answer when called upon feels embarrassing to me. Other students may look up to you when you answer questions correctly during recitations, so making even one mistake feels significant and unexpected. As a result, I hesitate to raise my hand, even when I know the answer, because my confidence has already been shaken.)

Research Question No. 2: How do these students cope with the challenges in learning mathematics under national learning camp?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about their strategies for coping with the challenges they faced in learning mathematics under learning camp. It was revealed that they employ a range of strategies and techniques to overcome these difficulties.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, 4 major themes emerged: Embodying the Practical Importance of Mathematics, Teacher Support and Motivation, Emulating Positive Mindset and Perseverance, and Practicing Self-Preparation Strategies.

Table 3. Students Cope with the Challenges in Learning Mathematics under National Learning Camp

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Embodying the Practical Importance of Mathematics	<p>“I am greatly motivated because I can relate it a lot to real-life situations in my life since math is always used. Mathematics is important to me even if it is challenging at times, but it is worth it because it greatly helps me.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“What motivates me is that it can used not only in school but also in real-life situations even if mathematics is challenging for me.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“In this day and age, we really need to study mathematics because it is very useful in our everyday lives and for me, that is what motivates me to continue learning.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“What motivates me is what our teacher tells us that math is not always difficult, and we can use it in real-life situations and those thoughts of ours that say math is difficult are just in our minds, but the truth is it's actually easy, and you just have to study.”-IDI-07</p>
Teacher Support and Motivation	<p>“You know, when our teacher appreciates even the small things, especially when we solve problems, and she helps me if I do not understand.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“You know when ma'am praises us through stories like 'thank you,' 'good job,' 'very good,' like that. That is what motivates us because ma'am also encourages us to study like that, so it boosts our motivation.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“She motivates me especially when even small things are appreciated by my teacher.” -IDI-08</p>
Emulating Positive Mindset and Perseverance	<p>“Well, it is all about fighting constantly, striving, and focusing while thinking positively because every math problem has a solution that just needs to be studied to understand.”- IDI-01</p> <p>“I always remind myself to think positively because I know I can overcome these challenges because, of course, every problem, especially in math, has a solution; it just requires patience and a love for mathematics.”- IDI-03</p> <p>“It's really just about answering myself that when things get tough sometimes, I shouldn't just break down too much because, through continuous learning, we eventually understand. When things get tough, just stay positive always because we also understand that if we ask for help from the teacher.”- IDI-06</p> <p>“I just put it in my mind that this too shall pass. I know that life is full of trials, so I understand myself not to surrender to life because I know that everything can be overcome through perseverance, as long as we always think positively and trust ourselves above all.”- IDI-14</p>
Practicing Self-Preparation Strategies	<p>“I always prepare myself every time I go to the learning camp because there is always a day to study and continue learning.”- IDI-04</p> <p>“You know, I prepare myself for the new lessons that I will learn because sometimes it takes me a long time to understand, so I need to prepare myself for the harder ones that will come or that I will encounter. That is why sometimes I study ahead at home so that I can participate in class the next day.” - IDI-06</p> <p>“You see, what I always prepare for is myself, especially when there's a class, like in the learning camp, because I shouldn't be late so I wake up early with the help of my mom. Then, I also prepare my school supplies like notebooks, papers, pens, and many more.”- IDI-07</p>

Embodying the Practical Importance of Mathematics

The focus of this theme revolves around embodying the practical importance of mathematics for students in learning mathematics under the learning camp. By showcasing real-world applications and demonstrating how mathematical concepts are relevant to everyday life, students can develop a deeper appreciation for the subject. Through hands-on activities, simulations, and interactive exercises tailored to their interests and experiences, students can see firsthand how mathematics is integral to various fields such as

science, technology, engineering, and finance. By emphasizing the practical significance of mathematics, educators can inspire students to engage more actively with the subject, fostering curiosity, motivation, and a greater sense of purpose in their mathematical learning journey within the learning camp.

During the interview, Fluent (pseudonym) expressed his strong motivation to learn mathematics, primarily fueled by its relevance to real-life situations. Despite the challenges posed by the subject, he emphasizes its importance due to its practical utility in various aspects of life. Additionally, Fluent showcases his determination to overcome obstacles and maintains a positive attitude towards learning and problem-solving. This combination of motivation, determination, and positivity reflects his commitment to mastering mathematics and leveraging its benefits in his everyday life. he mentioned:

“Na motivate ko ya samot na nga marelata nako siya sa tinuod nga sitwasyon sakong life kay gamit jud ang math kay always ta naga gamit ani. ang mathematics man gud para sakoa ya bisan og challenging siya tun an pero worth it kay dako siyag tabang sakoa ya.” (IDI-01)

(I am greatly motivated because I can relate it a lot to real-life situations in my life since math is always used. Mathematics is really important to me even if it's challenging at times, but it's worth it because it greatly helps me.)

As with the other participant, Dynamic (pseudonym) she is motivated by the prospect of applying mathematical concepts in real-life situations. This practical perspective suggests that her motivation to learn mathematics is driven by its potential to address real-world challenges and enhance problem-solving abilities beyond school. she shared:

“Ang nakapamotivate sakoa ya kay magamit ni siya sa dili lang sa skwela kundi mas gamit siya sa real-life situations kahit challenging ang mathematics para sakoa.” (IDI-03)

(What motivates me is that it can used not only in school but also in real-life situations even if mathematics is challenging for me.)

Moreover, Effortful (pseudonym) believed that studying mathematics is essential in today's world reflects her practical motivation to continue learning. She emphasizes the subject's usefulness in everyday life, highlighting its importance as a driving force behind her motivation to persist in her studies, she shared:

“Sa panahon karon ya, kailangan jud nato makatuon ug mathematics kay gamit kaayo na sa atong pang adlaw-adlaw na kinabuhi ug para sako mao na ang naga motivate sako para magpadayon ug tuon.” (IDI-04)

(In this day and age, we really need to study mathematics because it's very useful in our everyday lives and for me, that's what motivates me to continue learning.)

Lastly, Resourceful (pseudonym) emphasized the impact of her teacher's encouragement, highlighting the importance of positive reinforcement in overcoming perceived difficulties in mathematics. She acknowledges that the challenge often lies in one's mindset, recognizing the need for dedicated study to overcome mental barriers. This demonstrates her resilient and resourceful approach to learning, underscoring the role of self-perception and positive encouragement in fostering motivation and confidence. she stated:

“ahm, ang nakapa motivate sa akoo ya kay kanang mga ginaingon sa amoa sa maestra na dili lage daw lisod ang math og magamit daw ni namo sa tinuod nga sitwasyon og kuan kanang amoa ra daw nang utok na naga ingon na lisod ang math ya pero ang tinuod kay sayon ra daw, tapos matun an lang daw.” (IDI-07)

(What motivates me is what our teacher tells us that math is not always difficult and we can use it in real-life situations and those thoughts of ours that say math is difficult are just in our minds, but the truth is it's actually easy, and you just have to study.)

Teacher Support and Motivation

This theme focuses on providing teachers with the support and motivation to inspire students in learning mathematics under the learning camp. Recognizing the pivotal role educators play, the emphasis is on creating a supportive environment where teachers offer guidance, encouragement, and personalized assistance. By nurturing positive teacher-student relationships and fostering a growth mindset, educators empower students to overcome challenges and excel in mathematics within the learning camp.

During the interview, Active (pseudonym) stated that he values the importance of receiving appreciation from his teacher. He emphasized that even the smallest gestures make a difference to him. He highlighted the significance of his teacher's acknowledgment, particularly when he successfully solves problems or when she helps him understand concepts he struggles with. he mentioned:

“Kuan ya, kanang pag appreciate samong maestra sakoa maskin sa gamay na butang ilabi na og mag solve mi og pagtabang sakoa kung naa koy wala nasabtan ya.” (IDI-02)

(You know, when our teacher appreciates even the small things, especially when we solve problems and she helps me if I don't understand.)

As with the other participant, Passionate (pseudonym) expressed his appreciation for the motivational impact of praise from his teacher. He conveyed how the use of positive reinforcement, such as phrases like "thank you," "good job," and "very good," in stories shared

by his teacher, significantly motivates him and his peers. Additionally, Passionate (pseudonym) he highlighted that this form of encouragement not only acknowledges their efforts but also inspires them to continue studying diligently. he shared:

“Kuan ya kanang gina praise mi ni ma'am through ano kanang istorya ganing thank you, good job, very good, ana ya. Mao to nga ma motivate mi kay gina encourage sad mi ni ma'am ya nga magtuon ana so ma boost among motivation ana ya.” (IDI-06)

(You know when ma'am praises us through stories like 'thank you,' 'good job,' 'very good,' like that. That's what motivates us because ma'am also encourages us to study like that, so it boosts our motivation.)

Lastly, Cool Composure (pseudonym) shared that she feels motivated when her teacher appreciates even small efforts. This highlights the importance of recognition from teachers in boosting student motivation. she shared:

“makamotivate siya sa akua ya ilabi nan ga maskin gamay nabutang ya ma appreciate ko sa akog maestra “(IDI-08)

(She motivates me especially when even small things are appreciated by my teacher.)

Emulating Positive Mindset and Perseverance

The focus of this theme centers on emulating a positive mindset and perseverance among students in learning mathematics under the learning camp. By promoting resilience and a growth mindset, students are encouraged to view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles. Through guided practice, constructive feedback, and celebrating incremental progress, educators cultivate a supportive environment where students feel empowered to overcome setbacks and persist in their mathematical learning journey. By fostering a culture of perseverance and positivity, students develop the resilience and determination needed to tackle complex mathematical concepts and achieve academic success within the learning camp.

During the interview, Fluent (pseudonym) pointed out that he believes success in math requires constant effort, focus, and a positive mindset. He emphasized that every mathematical problem has a solution that can be understood through diligent study, he mentioned:

“Ahhmm Kanang laban lang permi ya, maningkamot Og focus lang og think positive kay tanan problema sa math ya naay solution nga need lang jud studyhan para makabalo.” (IDI-01)

(Well, it's all about fighting constantly, striving, and focusing while thinking positively because every math problem has a solution that just needs to be studied to understand.)

As with the other participant, Dynamic (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of maintaining a positive mindset. She believes in overcoming challenges by reminding herself that every problem, especially in math, has a solution, requiring patience and a love for mathematics. she shared:

“I always remind myself ya na think positive lang that makabalo rako og makaya nako na malampasan ni na challenges kay ang syempre ya wala may problema na walay sulosyon same sa math, there will always a solution pero need lang jud og pasensya na tunan og e love ang mathematics.” (IDI-03)

(I always remind myself to think positively because I know I can overcome these challenges because, of course, every problem, especially in math, has a solution; it just requires patience and a love for mathematics.)

In addition, Passionate (pseudonym) reflected on the importance of staying positive and resilient during tough times. He emphasized the value of continuous learning, suggesting that understanding comes with perseverance. he mentioned:

“Kuan rajud ya kanang sabton lang jud nako akong kaugalingon nga kanang maglisod gani pud ta usahay then dili lang pud mag breakdown gani kaayo ya kay sa sige natog tuon ana kay makasabot raman sad ta kadugayan ya. Pag naami kalisod kay stay positive lang jud always pud ya kay makasabot raman pud mi if mag patabang nami sa teacher ana.” (IDI-06)

(It's really just about answering myself that when things get tough sometimes, I shouldn't just break down too much because, through continuous learning, we eventually understand. When things get tough, just stay positive always because we also understand that if we ask for help from the teacher.)

Lastly, Optimistic (pseudonym) she emphasized the importance of maintaining a hopeful outlook in the face of adversity. She adopts the mindset that difficult times are temporary and will eventually pass. Additionally, Optimistic (pseudonym) she acknowledges the inevitable challenges in life but refuses to surrender to them, instead choosing perseverance as the path to overcoming obstacles. he stated:

“Gina put lng jud nako sa akong mind ya mulabay ra ni. Kabalo mn ko nga ang kinabuhi puno jud ug pagsulay mao ng ginabot nako akong sarili jud para dili ko musurrender sa akong kinabuhi kay kabalo mn ko nga makaya ra nig labang tanan pagsulay basta think positive lang jud ta always og saligan permi ang kaugalingon labaw pa sa tanan.” (IDI-14)

(I just put it in my mind that this too shall pass. I know that life is full of trials, so I understand myself not to surrender to life because I know that everything can be overcome through perseverance, as long as we always think positively and trust ourselves above all.)

Practicing Self-Preparation Strategies

This theme focuses on equipping students in learning mathematics under the learning camp with effective self-preparation strategies. By providing guidance on goal-setting, time management, and study techniques, students learn to take ownership of their learning. Through these skills, students become more independent and better equipped to excel in mathematics within the learning camp.

During the interview, Effortful (pseudonym) she emphasized the importance of preparing herself before attending the learning camp. She recognizes that each camp day is an opportunity for studying and advancing her learning, hence the need for consistent readiness. she mentioned:

" Ang akong kaugalingon akong gina-andam everytime moadto ko'g learning camp ya kay naa napud adlaw para magtuon ug magpadayon." (IDI-04)

(I always prepare myself every time I go to the learning camp because there's always a day to study and continue learning.)

Moreover, Passionate (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of self-preparation for upcoming lessons. He acknowledged that understanding certain topics may take time, so he takes proactive measures to prepare himself for more challenging material., he mentioned:

"Kuan ya kanang gina prepare nako akong kuagalingon sa mga new lessons nga akong matun-nan ya kay usahay baya dugay kaayo ko makasabot so need nako iprepare akong kagalingon nga naapay mas lisod pa nga moabot or maagian nako maong usahay mag study najud ko daan sa balay ya para kay pagka ugma maka participate ko sa klase." (IDI-06)

(You know, I prepare myself for the new lessons that I will learn because sometimes it takes me a long time to understand, so I need to prepare myself for the harder ones that will come or that I will encounter. That's why sometimes I study ahead at home so that I can participate in class the next day.)

Furthermore, Resourceful (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of self-preparation, especially for classes like those in the learning camp. She stressed the need for punctuality, waking up early with her mother's help. Additionally, she organizes her school supplies to ensure readiness for the day's activities. she shared:

"kuan ahm ang gina prepare jud nako perme kay kanang akong sarili, ya na dapat inig naay klase katong sa ano sa learning camp kay dapat dili ko ma late maong ginapukaw ko sa akong mama. Tapos kuan sad, mga um gamit sad sa eskwelahan paras anang kuan notebook, kanang papel, ballpen ug daghan pa." (IDI-07)

(You see, what I always prepare for is myself, especially when there's a class, like in the learning camp, because I shouldn't be late so I wake up early with the help of my mom. Then, I also prepare my school supplies like notebooks, papers, pens, and many more.)

Research Question No. 3: What insights can be obtained from these students who are learning mathematics under national learning camp that can be shared to other students and to the academe in general?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to share their insights about the students in learning mathematics under learning camp.

Table 4. Insights from these Students who are Learning Mathematics under National Learning Camp

Emerging Themes	Supporting Statements
Reflections on the Importance of Active Learning and Persistence	"You know, it is really important for us to listen and strive to learn so that we can understand things more easily, and it's also more enjoyable because I learned while doing activities and playing math games." - IDI-01 "What I realized is that we need to strive to learn and give our best in class. This is what I learned from the learning camp." - IDI-04
Perseverance and Growth Mindset in Mathematics	"You know, I also realized that schooling is really different, even if it's hard because what's important is to persevere. And I also realized that schooling isn't really that difficult if we just work hard." - IDI-07 "What I want to tell other students attending the learning camp is to just keep going. We all face difficulties that we cannot escape, and the best solution to this is to confront them with effort and determination until they are resolved." - IDI-04 "You know, just continue participating in the learning camp because it can help enhance your learning in math through activities that you enjoy in the learning camp. They can learn even more when they participate in this learning camp in the future." - IDI-06 "Just keep going and never give up. Mathematics can be difficult, but with hard work, it will become easier for you." - IDI-09 "Just continue with schooling. There will come a time when we will be favored. Let's just consider that all trials in our lives will pass. And there should be study habits because math is really difficult, especially if you can't retain the concept." - IDI-14
Integration of Technology for Enhanced Engagement and Learning	"What I suggest is for teachers to use various types of technology to improve teaching. It would be better if teachers utilize different technologies like interactive PowerPoint and videos." - IDI-06 "Create engaging activities that can be useful for us students and integrate technology for better understanding, and to have a lot of fun using technology." - IDI-09

Overcoming Math Challenges Through Effort and Engagement

"I encourage my classmates to strive because learning can be enjoyable, especially when there are technologies to motivate us to be active in class, especially with new challenges."- IDI-10

"Perhaps learning math may seem difficult at first, but it might just be a matter of interest and effort. With interest and determination, math can probably be understood." - IDI-05

"Based on my experiences, I can say that math isn't really difficult if you just try to understand it and actively participate. When you participate, you are more encouraged to continue learning math despite the difficulties with certain topics, because in the end, you'll learn." - IDI-05

"Despite the challenges I've faced, I've realized that math isn't actually difficult as long as you put in effort to understand it. I personally looked for ways to understand better and not forget what I've learned in my schooling. Then, I listened more attentively and participated more in class because that's also my way to learn and understand better."- IDI-05

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: Reflections on the Importance of Active Learning and Persistence, Perseverance and Growth Mindset in Mathematics, Integration of Technology for Enhanced Engagement and Learning, and Overcoming Math Challenges Through Effort and Engagement.

Reflections on the Importance of Active Learning and Persistence

This theme focuses on emphasizing the importance of active learning and persistence among students in learning mathematics under the learning camp. Through active engagement in hands-on activities and collaborative projects, students deepen their understanding and develop critical skills. Additionally, fostering persistence and resilience empowers students to overcome challenges, building confidence and paving the way for success within the learning camp.

During the interview, Fluent (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of active engagement and experiential learning in the process of understanding mathematical concepts. By expressing the importance of listening attentively and actively striving to learn, he underscores a proactive approach to mathematical learning, he mentioned:

"Kuan ya kanang importsnte jud diay nga maminaw ta og maningkamot nga makatuon para dali rata makasabot og kanang mas lingaw sad siya ya kay nakatuom ko habang naga activity og mga padula sa math." (IDI-01)

(You know, it's really important for us to listen and strive to learn so that we can understand things more easily, and it's also more enjoyable because I learned while doing activities and playing math games.)

As with the other participant, Effortful (pseudonym) Effortful emphasized the importance of striving to learn and giving her best in class, drawing from insights gained during the learning camp. This statement underscores the value of dedication and hard work in academic pursuits, she shared:

"Ang akong narealize ya kay kailangan nato maningkamot para makatuon ug ihatag atong best sa klasi. Mao ni akong natun an sa learning camp ya" (IDI-04)

(What I realized is that we need to strive to learn and give our best in class. This is what I learned from the learning camp.)

Lastly, Resourceful (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of perseverance and hard work in overcoming the challenges of schooling. By acknowledging the difficulty of academic endeavors while emphasizing the importance of persistence, she highlighted a resilient attitude towards learning. Additionally, her realization that schooling becomes more manageable with dedication and effort underscores the transformative power of perseverance, she shared:

"kanang ano kanang na realize ra pod nako sa akong sarili ya na lahi rajud diay ang mag eskwela, kanang bahalag lisod kay ang importante jud kay kanang magpadayon." (IDI-07)

(You know, I also realized that schooling is really different, even if it's hard because what's important is to persevere. And I also realized that schooling isn't really that difficult if we just work hard.)

Perseverance and Growth Mindset in Mathematics

This theme focuses on on fostering perseverance and a growth mindset among students in learning mathematics under the learning camp. By promoting the belief that intelligence and abilities can be developed through dedication and effort, students are encouraged to embrace challenges and view mistakes as opportunities for growth. Through guided practice, constructive feedback, and celebrating incremental progress, educators cultivate an environment where students feel empowered to persist in the face of difficulty. By instilling a growth mindset, students develop the resilience and determination needed to tackle complex mathematical concepts and excel within the learning camp.

During the interview, Effortful (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of perseverance and determination in facing challenges encountered during the learning camp. Her advice to fellow students reflects a resilient mindset, encouraging them to persist in the face of difficulties rather than avoiding or succumbing to them, she mentioned:

“Ang ako maingon sa uban estudyante ya nga nagtuon sa learning camp is magpadayon lang mo. Kitang tanan magkaagi'g kalisud ug di nato kini matakasan, ang pinakamaayong solusyon ani kay atubangon ug paningkamotan na masolusyonan.” (IDI-04)

(What I want to tell other students attending the learning camp is to just keep going. We all face difficulties that we cannot escape, and the best solution to this is to confront them with effort and determination until they are resolved.)

As with the other participant, Passionate (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of continued participation in the learning camp to enhance mathematical learning. His advice suggests that engaging in activities within the camp can contribute positively to learning experiences, particularly in mathematics. Passionate (pseudonym) highlights the potential for increased learning through active participation in future camp sessions, he shared:

“Kuan ya kanang padayon gihapon ug apil sa learning camp kay makatabang siya nga ma enhance imong learning sa math through sa mga activities nga masinati nimo sa learning camp ya. Mas maka learn pa sila pag mag participate sila aning learning camp in the future.” (IDI-06)

(You know, just continue participating in the learning camp because it can help enhance your learning in math through activities that you enjoy in the learning camp. They can learn even more when they participate in this learning camp in the future.)

In addition, Vocabulary (pseudonym) reflected on the importance of persistence and perseverance in learning mathematics. Her advice underscores the notion that while mathematics may pose challenges, continuous effort and determination can lead to mastery. By encouraging others to persist and not give up, Vocabulary highlights the belief that with dedication and hard work, the difficulties associated with mathematics can be overcome., she mentioned:

“Just keep going and never give up, mathematics can be difficult but with hardwork it would become easie for you.” (IDI-09)

(Just keep going and never give up. Mathematics can be difficult, but with hard work, it will become easier for you.)

Lastly, Optimistic (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of perseverance in education. Her advice encourages students to persist despite challenges, believing that favorable outcomes will eventually come. She highlighted the significance of developing effective study habits, particularly in mathematics, where retaining concepts can be challenging, she stated:

“padayon lng jud sa pagskwela ya, muabot ra ang panahon nga kita na sad ang paboran. Ato lng isipon nga mulabay ra tanan pagsulay sa atong kinabuhi. Ug dapat naa nay study habits jud ya kay ang math lisud jud siya labi nag dli nimo ma retain ang concept.” (IDI-14)

(Just continue with schooling. There will come a time when we will be favored. Let's just consider that all trials in our lives will pass. And there should be study habits because math is really difficult, especially if you can't retain the concept.)

Integration of Technology for Enhanced Engagement and Learning

This theme focuses on integrating technology to enhance engagement and learning among students in learning mathematics under the learning camp. By utilizing digital tools such as simulations, tutorials, and educational apps, students engage with mathematical concepts dynamically. The integration of technology fosters personalized learning experiences, promoting active participation and improving overall mathematical proficiency within the camp.

During the interview, Passionate (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of integrating technology into teaching practices. His suggestion highlights the potential benefits of utilizing various types of technology, such as interactive PowerPoint presentations and videos, to enhance the learning experience, he mentioned:

“Kuan ya akong ma suggest kay mag gamit ug klase-klase nga technology gani ya kay para mas nindot ang pagtudlo sa teachers pag naami gani makita nga lahi-lahi nga technologies like kanang mga interactive powerpoint tas video ana.” (IDI-06)

(What I suggest is for teachers to use various types of technology to improve teaching. It would be better if teachers utilize different technologies like interactive PowerPoint and videos.)

Moreover, Effortful (pseudonym) reflected on the importance of incorporating engaging activities and technology into learning experiences. Her suggestion emphasizes the need for activities that are both educational and enjoyable for students, she mentioned:

“Make and engaging activity that can be useful to us student and also integrating a technology for better understanding and have a lot of fun using technology.” (IDI-09)

(Create engaging activities that can be useful for us students and integrate technology for better understanding, and to have a lot of fun using technology.)

Lastly, Smart Joker (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of encouraging classmates to strive for excellence in learning. His statement underscores the notion that learning can be enjoyable, particularly when supported by technologies that foster active engagement in the classroom, he stated:

“kuan ya kanang I encourage nako ang uban na kaila o classmate nako na maningkamot kay lingaw man habang magtuon tapos unta naay mga technology ya para maing ganyo mi og maging active sa klase samot na ya bag o samoa.” (IDI-10)

(I encourage my classmates to strive because learning can be enjoyable, especially when there are technologies to motivate us to be active in class, especially with new challenges.)

Overcoming Math Challenges Through Effort and Engagement

This theme focuses on students in learning mathematics under the learning camp overcoming math challenges through effort and engagement. By emphasizing the importance of perseverance and active involvement, this theme underscores the idea that success in mathematics is achievable through dedication and participation. Through guided practice, collaborative activities, and hands-on learning experiences, students are empowered to confront and overcome mathematical obstacles. By fostering a supportive environment that encourages effort and engagement, educators equip students with the tools and mindset needed to tackle complex mathematical concepts and thrive within the learning camp.

During the interview, Caring (pseudonym) pointed out the potential misconception surrounding the difficulty of learning mathematics. His statement suggests that while math may initially appear challenging, it could simply require a combination of interest and effort to comprehend, he mentioned:

“Nga kaya raman jud siguro tun an ang math ya lisod lang jud siya pero inig tagaan nimog interest og kakugi kay kaya siguro ang math ya.” (IDI-05)

(Perhaps learning math may seem difficult at first, but it might just be a matter of interest and effort. With interest and determination, math can probably be understood.)

Moreover, Passionate (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of active participation and understanding in learning mathematics. His statement reflects personal experiences that suggest math becomes more manageable with effort and engagement., he mentioned:

“Through sa akong mga experiences nga nasinati ya no kay makaingon ko nga dili man lisod ang math if imohang sabton lang jud ug kanang maminaw tas mag participate lang jud kay once nga magparticipate ka ya kay mas ma encourage ka nga magpadayon ug tuon sa math despite sa mga kalisod sa mga topics kay at the end makatuon rajud ka.” (IDI-06)

(Based on my experiences, I can say that math isn't really difficult if you just try to understand it and actively participate. When you participate, you are more encouraged to continue learning math despite the difficulties with certain topics, because in the end, you'll learn.)

Lastly, Optimistic (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of effort and active engagement in learning mathematics. Her statement reflects a positive outlook on overcoming challenges, suggesting that with dedication and perseverance, math becomes more manageable, she stated:

“Despite sa akong mga naagian ya, nakaingon ko nga dli mn diay lisod ang math basta magkugi lng kag sabot jud. Ako na mismo nangitaan paraan para mas makasabot ko ug dli nako makalimtan akong nga natun an sa akong pagskwela. Then mas nagapaminaw ug nagaparticipate nako sa klase kay mao sad ni akong way para mas makabalo ug makatuon.” (IDI-14)

(Despite the challenges I've faced, I've realized that math isn't actually difficult as long as you put in effort to understand it. I personally looked for ways to understand better and not forget what I've learned in my schooling. Then, I listened more attentively and participated more in class because that's also my way to learn and understand better.)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study concludes that the participants had a variety of experiences that pointed to their challenges, stories of coping, and certain realizations about learning mathematics in the learning camp. These could mean that there are students who require both peer assistance and teacher support.

Furthermore, students in the learning camp motivation to learn is greatly influenced by their social and family lives. students' emotional behavior is also disturbed because they are under pressure from their surroundings. This poses a risk to their health, particularly their mental and emotional health, because it could put them in danger or result in an unlikely outcome. The researcher also found out that these students are Emulating Positive Mindset and Perseverance in learning mathematics in the learning camp. As a result, they see this as an opportunity and motivation to do better every day.

In addition, the students in learning mathematics in the learning camp are also suffering lack of self-confidence causing learning deficiency. Students are also vulnerable in many challenges just like other students. They also have different ways of coping up which makes them unique in achieving their high potential in mathematics subject in the class.

Finally, the researcher concludes that students have a variety of stories to tell about their experiences in learning mathematics in the learning camp, coping mechanisms, and various challenges as they strive for overcoming math challenges.

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